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The effect of acid-assisted ionic liquid pretreatment on the fermentable sugar and silica production of rice husks

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計畫編號： MOST 106-2218-E-110-009-MY2

1. Introduction

Rice husks (RHs) are tough and bulky with high silica content and account for approximately 20 wt% of the mass of rice. Rice production worldwide is approximately 740 million tons per year, which indicates that approximately 148 million tons of RHs are produced (Barana et al., 2016). RHs comprise a large amount of ash and lignin, which hinder RHs toward biological and environmental threat. The use of RHs has been limited because of their bulkiness and low levels of nutrition. Therefore, RHs are generally burned or buried. However, this causes particle pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, a waste of energy, and consumption of landfill space.

To overcome the aforementioned disadvantages of RHs, several studies have focused on the production of high-value chemicals (Barana et al., 2016). Ionic liquids (ILs), used as a green solvent for dissolving lignocellulosic biomass, have numerous advantages such as chemical and thermal stability, low volatility, and easy recyclability (Badgajar and Bhanage, 2015). Unfortunately, a large amount of the IL cannot penetrate the surface of RHs covered with silica and then dissolve cellulose; a high temperature and long process is required to dissolve cellulose (Yu et al., 2014).

In this study, the potential of this process for using RHs to produce SiO₂ and fermentable sugar was investigated. Field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) was performed to analyze the morphology and structural features of RHs in different pretreatments, which may demonstrate the mechanisms that improve process efficiency.

2. Materials and methods

(1) Pretreatment and recovery of rice husks

A BMIMCl solution containing 1.2 wt% hydrochloric acid and 20 wt% water was

added to a 250-mL round-bottom flask. A total of 5.19 g of RHs (5.0 g dry biomass) was transferred to the flask and well mixed. The solid to liquid weight ratio was 1:10. A heating element equipped with a magnetic stirring device was used to preheat the mixture to 130°C. A washing process was repeated five times to remove the IL and acid from the biomass. The recovered biomass was dried at 60°C for 24 h

(2) Enzymatic hydrolysis

Pretreated and untreated RHs of 2.5% w/v were suspended in 0.05 M sodium citrate buffer (pH of 4.8) containing 0.02% sodium azide, a cellulose complex (Novozyme NS220086) enzyme loading of 50 FPU/g solid substrate, and a β -glucosidase (Novozyme NS221118) enzyme loading of 40 CBU/g solid substrate. Enzymatic hydrolysis was performed at 50°C in a horizontal shaker and incubator for 48 h at a rotation speed of 150 rpm. Cellulose conversion was calculated as follows:

Cellulose conversion (%)

$$= \frac{\text{Reduction sugar produced through enzymatic hydrolysis} \times 0.9}{\text{Holocellulose in solid substrate}} \times 100$$

Pyrolysis was performed at 700°C for 2 h. The product of pyrolysis was collected and sealed in a 1.5-mL centrifuge tube for chemical composition analysis.

(3) Morphological analysis and characterization

SEM images were obtained using a JEOL JSM-7001F SEM. The samples were sputter-coated with a thin layer (ca. 3 nm) of Au/Pd before SEM imaging.

3. Results and discussion

(1) Enzymatic hydrolysis of rice husks for reducing sugar production

Fig. 1 shows the result of enzymatic hydrolysis of RHs using different methods. The cellulose conversion of HCl-treated and pure-IL-treated RHs was slightly increased compared with that of raw RHs. However, the BMIMCl pretreatment combined with a low concentration of HCl showed considerable enhancement in RH saccharification. The low reducing sugar production of HCl-treated RHs was primarily because of the lower severity compared with the conventional diluted acid pretreatment (Hsu et al., 2010). Moreover, after a pure BMIMCl treatment for 8 h, the RHs did not exhibit significant enhancement in enzymatic hydrolysis, with 89.32% solid recovery. Because the silicon on the surface of RHs hindered the reaction between cellulose and the IL, the severity of the BMIMCl pretreatment in this study was not efficient to deconstruct the structure of the RHs. However, the BMIMCl-HCl-treated RHs yielded 26.83%

cellulose conversion after 48 h of hydrolysis, which was 4.8–7.6 times higher than that obtained with the other pretreatments. An aqueous IL combined with low concentration of an acid, such as HCl, has a significant effect on the pretreatment of various materials containing lignocellulose. HCl acts as a catalyst in removing hemicellulose and breaking up the structure of RHs; subsequently, the IL can more easily dissolve cellulose.

Fig. 1. The enzymatic hydrolysis of the RHs in different pretreatments

(2) Scanning electron microscopy analysis

To determine the effect of pretreatment on the morphology of the treated RHs, SEM analyses was conducted. Fig. 2 shows SEM images of the untreated, HCl-treated, BMIMCl-treated, and BMIMCl-HCl-treated RHs under 2000 \times magnification. The surface of the raw RHs was covered with regular and rigid silica, which is indicated in grey (Fig. 2a). Accessing and utilizing lignocellulose in RHs is difficult for enzymes and microorganisms because of the sturdy structure of RHs. Although the surface of the HCl-treated RHs exhibited chip-piece shapes, the outer layer of silica and the cellulose skeleton were retained (Fig. 2b). In the BMIMCl treatment, the obstacle to break up the complex structure was also observed (Fig. 2c); however, the outer silica layer had leaked, and some amount of the grey material had been eliminated. The BMIMCl-HCl-treated RHs exhibited a more porous structure and irregular surface than the RHs obtained using other pretreatments. The outer silica layer was completely disbanded, and regenerated cellulose had precipitated on the sample surface (Fig. 2d). Cellulose that was more exposed was directly approached by the enzyme, which explains the high cellulose conversion determined in the enzymatic hydrolysis experiment. HCl can thus assist BMIMCl in the dissolution of cellulose over a short period, penetrating the rigid outer silica layer.

Fig. 2 SEM images of RHs with different pretreatment methods under 2000 magnification. (a) Untreated; (b) HCl treated; (c) BMIMCl treated; (d) BMIMCl-HCl treated.

4. Conclusion

This study indicates that BMIMCl–HCl pretreatment is an effective method of utilizing RHs for producing fermentable sugar and amorphous silica nanoparticles. The BMIMCl–HCl treatment of RHs has a synergistic effect on the deconstruction of RHs' lignocellulosic structure and the elimination of ionic metals. A high concentration of fermentable sugar and pure silica were obtained in a short time and with a low IL loading, which ensures low processing costs.

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